

Effect of Black Polyethylene Mulch on Pineapple Yield and Farmer Perceptions under On-Farm Conditions in Sidama Region, Ethiopia

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between both authors. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Abstract

Pineapple is an important tropical fruit crop that demonstrates a degree of drought tolerance despite its shallow root system and contributes significantly to household nutrition and diet diversity. This study evaluated the effect of black polyethylene mulch on growth performance and economic yield of pineapple under farmer-managed conditions in Aletachuko district, Sidama Region. Farmers were selected purposively based on production potential, land availability, willingness of the farmers to implement full package of technology, aware effect of black Polyethylene on soil and health and sharing their knowledge to other farmers with collaboration of Woreda and Kebele agricultural experts. A field demonstration was implemented on 20 volunteer farmers' field; where each plot (100 m²) was divided into mulched and non-mulched treatments. Results indicated a substantial yield advantage from mulching, with an average yield of 89.04 tons ha⁻¹, significantly higher than the traditional practice. Farmers' attitudes, perceptions, and opinions toward the mulching technology were assessed using a five-point Likert scale. The majority of respondents

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either strongly agreed or agreed that the mulching technology helped retain soil moisture (63.59%), increased productivity (91%), improved fruit taste (63.6), marketable (81.7%) and was easy to apply (81.7%) whereas without mulching soil moisture (10.89%), increased productivity (36.29%), reduced weed pressure (3.5%), marketable (29%) and was easy to apply (9.02%). So the results revealed majority of them reported positive perceptions, highlighting improved soil moisture retention, reduced weed pressure, and improved productivity, marketable. Although the technology was promising, adoption may be constrained by the cost and availability of polythene sheets in the area. Moreover, concern about the potential environmental impacts of plastic sheet on soil biodiversity and micro-flora need further research.

Keywords: Pineapple; black-polyethylene; demonstration; yield improvement.

1. Introduction

Pineapple (*Ananas comosus* (L.) (Merr) is an important tropical fruit crop valued for its rich nutritional content, including vitamin C, dietary fiber, and high water content. Its regular consumption contributes to improved dietary diversity and overall health. The crop is well adapted to a wide range of agro-climatic conditions, thriving in both tropical and subtropical environments (Agri Farming, 2024; Zenebe et al., 2024). In addition to its nutritional importance, pineapple also plays a role in environmental conservation. Its dense canopy structure contributes to reduce soil erosion and supports carbon sequestration; these make it suitable for integration into agroforestry systems, a common land-use practice in the Sidama region and Gedeo Zone.

Optimal pineapple production requires soils rich in organic matter, which improve nutrient availability and water retention. Proper land/soil preparation, including loosening the soil and incorporating organic/compost or inorganic fertilizers, is essential for achieving good yields. Balanced plant nutrition, particularly adequate supply of macronutrients (nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium) and essential micronutrients (such as magnesium and calcium), is critical for healthy growth and development.

In Mexico, has been developed a new pineapple crop managementsystem called “Intensive pineapple production in protected environment”, which among other practices is based upon the use of soil plastic cover in order to create microclimatic conditions more favorable for pineapple crop development (Uriza-Ávila et al., 2018; Reinhardt et al., 2019; Belew et al., 2022; Beyene et al., 2021; Legesse et al., 2024).

In Ethiopia, pineapple production is largely small-scale and labor-intensive, with limited growers engaged in commercial farming. Recommended planting density of pineapple is about 44,444 plants per hectare, depending on market preferences for fruit size (MoALR, 2017). Reported yields are about 84 tons per hectare under research field conditions and 63.4 tons per hectare on farmers’ fields (MoALR, 2017), indicating a considerable yield gap. This gap shows the need for improved production practices and the adoption of innovative technologies along the value chain.

In Ethiopia the soil degradation, insect pest and different weed species problem became a serious crop yield reducing factors. So that farmers use over dose application of inorganic chemicals which resulted minimizing of pollinating agents, pollution and health problems. To achieve this, producers are applying fertilizers and pesticides over dosage to increase yield. However, such excess application of inorganic chemicals have negative side effects directly on soil organisms and indirectly on every living things; polluting water sources, air and soil (Ranjan et al., 2017). In Sidama Region part of Ethiopia such problems are practical.

Even so, due to these explanations, natural capabilities (like soil and water) are being perpetually under pressure and demands an organized and fine spun access to enhance the fruitfulness of agricultural crops. In the light of the preceding, various queries originate in the mindset viz. How to accelerate the yield of agriculture without using the surplus fertilizers and chemicals? How to reduce the degradation of soils? How to maintain the moisture in the soil? How to manage the weeds in our fields? How is the addition of nutrients to our soils?

Plastic mulching offers several perks, including insulating the soil, improving soil structure, and controlling weeds. mulch film for pineapple helps in insulating the soil by retaining the required amount of heat. This is particularly helpful for plants that cannot withstand cold temperatures like vegetables. It also helps in the growth of perennial fruits that don’t normally grow during winter. Another advantage is that it helps in improving the

structure of the soil. This is because it prevents people and animals from walking on it, so it cannot easily clamp together. As a result, there is improved aeration that promotes plant growth. Controlling the growth of weed is also another advantage and soil mulching (Neim et al., 2021) Among these practices, soil mulching, especially using plastic film, has shown promising potential. In addition, mulch raises the soil temperature, which changes the physical and chemical composition of the soil, promoting early harvest and faster crop development. Moreover, it improves plant growth speed and increases water retention capacity (Serrano-Ruiz, 2021).

A study by Neim *et al.* (2021) indicated that black plastic mulch and coffee husk mulch effectively suppress weed growth and increase pineapple yield. Furthermore, Coelho *et al.* (2024) found that soil water availability under plastic mulch remained above 80% during the crop cycle, compared to 15 -70% in non -mulched plots.

Despite these promising findings, there is limited on-farm evidence regarding the performance and acceptability of plastic mulching under local farmer conditions in Aletachuko district of the Sidama region. Therefore, this demonstration study was undertaken to evaluate the effect of black plastic/ Black Polyethylene mulch on pineapple productivity under farmer conditions, assess farmers' perception on these technologies, and evaluate on-farm pineapple yield performance.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Description of the Study Area

The demonstration was conducted in Aletachuko district, located in the Sidama Regional State of Ethiopia. The district is bordered by Dara district to the south, Wallame district (Oromia region) to the southwest, Loka Abaya to the west, Dale to the north, and Aleta Wondo to the east. It comprises 26 rural and 5 urban kebeles.

Agro-ecologically, Aletachuko is predominantly *midland* locations (approximately 70%), with the remaining area classified as *kolla*. Altitude ranges from 1,400 to 2,000 meters above sea level (m.a.s.l.), with mean annual temperatures between 22°C and 28°C and annual rainfall ranging from 1,400 to 2,300 mm. Geographically, the district is situated between 38°13'0"E to 38°21'01"E longitude and 6°27'0"N to 6°34'0"N latitude.

2.2 Site and Farmer Selection

Before conducting the demonstration, researchers from Hawassa Agricultural Research Center (HARC) and experts from the Aletachuko District Agriculture Office introduced the objectives of the activity, which was supported by ISVCD project. Following this, two kebeles, namely Gambela and Tesso, were selected based on their potential for pineapple production.

Participant farmers were carefully chosen in collaboration with kebele development agents (DAs) using the following selection criteria and willingness to adopt and evaluate new technologies, openness to data sharing and peer-to-peer learning, availability of suitable land for demonstration, and proximity to roads for easy accessibility.

A total of 20 farmers (10 from each kebele) were selected, 40% of whom were female -headed households. Additionally, two Farmer Training Centers (FTCs), one in each kebele, were involved in the demonstration.

2.3 Demonstration Approach

Training: Before the field activities began, selected farmers, development agents, and district experts participated in theoretical and practical training. Topics of the training covered general pineapple agronomic practices, the benefits of black plastic mulching, management of demonstration plots, post -harvest handling, and fruit quality improvement strategies.

Treatments and Experimental Design: Twelve farmers with adjacent plots were purposively selected for the demonstration. Each farmer received 120 pineapple suckers of Smooth Cayenne cultivar. Demonstration plots were measured 10 × 10 m (100 m²) and were divided into two equal treatments:

Treatment 1: Pineapple planted with black plastic mulch

Treatment 2 (control): Pineapple planted without mulch (traditional practice)

A total of 1,500 suckers were planted with mulch and 1,500 without mulch across all participating plots in April 2022, during the *Belg* cropping season. Planting was carried out on ridges spaced at 1.5 meters apart, with an intra-row spacing of 0.6 meters. After planting, proper field management practices, including weeding, compost application, and pest control, were applied uniformly across all plots to ensure consistent growing conditions.

Fig. 1. Comparison of pineapple field demonstrations under plastic mulch (left) and conventional (non-mulched) practice (right)

2.4 Data Collection and Analysis

The demonstration sites were regularly monitored by researchers in accordance with the milestone objectives outlined during project proposal development. Field visits and showcasing events were organized for both mulched and non-mulched pineapple plots, involving farmers, development agents, district agricultural office experts, researchers, and media personnel. During these events, participants shared their feedback and reflections on the performance of the technologies. Both quantitative and qualitative data were collected. Qualitative data were gathered through field observations, farmer preference rankings, household interviews, and focus group discussions (FGDs). Quantitative data included measurements such as fruit yield, input costs, and economic returns.

The collected data were analyzed using simple descriptive statistical methods. Farmers' preferences were evaluated using a ranking matrix, where responses were scored and mean values were used to rank each preference criterion.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Gender Inclusiveness

During the initial training session, a total of 47 participants were involved, the majority of whom were farmers, followed by development agents and other experts (Fig. 1). In terms of gender inclusiveness, female participation was higher in Teso Kebele than in Gambela Kebele. This localized variation in female farmer engagement is consistent with observations in other parts of Ethiopia, where participation often fluctuates based on regional social norms and household labor allocations (Mersha, 2018).

However, no female researchers took part in the training sessions, indicating a significant gap in gender representation. This mirrors a broader national challenge within the Ethiopian agricultural research system, where female professional representation remains notably low compared to their male counterparts (Gezahegn et al., 2021). The absence of female researchers in this study was primarily due to the limited number of female experts stationed at the research center during the design and implementation phases—a structural issue previously identified as a barrier to gender-responsive technology dissemination in the country (Tavener et al., 2019).

Fig. 2. Comparison of female participation in training sessions between two kebeles

3.2 Field Day Participation and Reflections

Similar to the training sessions, women's participation during the field day event was significantly lower than that of men. This gender disparity in agricultural field days is a common challenge in Ethiopia, often attributed to domestic labor burdens and limited access to extension information for female-headed households (Mersha, 2018). Despite this imbalance, the field day achieved a high turnout of farmers, particularly those targeted for scaling the black plastic mulch technology. The presence of experts and local political leaders at various levels played a supportive role in promoting and potentially scaling up the demonstrated innovation, reflecting the importance of multi-stakeholder engagement in Ethiopian technology adoption (Dermas, 2017).

During the field day discussions, farmers expressed a strong interest in adopting and expanding the use of black plastic mulching technology. They also emphasized the necessity of linking pineapple production with nearby agro-processing facilities, such as those in Yirgalem and Gedeo, to enhance market access and value addition.

Insights from focus group discussions revealed several perceived benefits of using plastic mulch. Farmers who participated in the technology demonstration reported that pineapple fruit yields nearly doubled compared to non-mulched plots. They also noted that weed pressure was significantly reduced, soil moisture was better conserved, and fruits showed improved taste and flavor. These findings are consistent with results from Southwest Ethiopia, where mulching has been shown to improve both the physical yield and the chemical quality of the fruit (Neim et al., 2021). Ultimately, these improvements translated into higher household income from the mulched plots.

Despite these benefits, the field day event reflected broader social and cultural constraints, particularly the limited involvement of women in research and leadership roles. This pattern is consistent with findings in other regions of Ethiopia, where institutional and cultural barriers often limit female engagement in formal agricultural extension and decision-making processes (Gezahegn et al., 2021). This constraint was evident in the relatively low female participation observed in both the training sessions and field day activities in Aleta Chuko. Similar trends have been documented in Northern Ethiopia, where female-headed households often face greater time poverty and less access to innovative technology demonstrations compared to their male counterparts (Tavener et al., 2019; Mersha, 2018).

3.3 Innovation Preference Score

Farmers' attitudes, perceptions, and opinions toward the mulching technology were assessed using a five-point Likert scale (strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree) across seven evaluation indicators

(Table 1). The majority of respondents either strongly agreed or agreed that the mulching technology helped retain soil moisture (63.59%), increased productivity (91%), improved fruit taste (63.6), marketable (81.7%) and was easy to apply (81.7%) whereas without mulching soil moisture (10.89%), increased productivity (36.29%), reduced weed pressure (3.5%), marketable (29%) and was easy to apply (9.02%). These positive perceptions are consistent with studies conducted in the Central Highlands and Southwest Ethiopia, where smallholders have increasingly recognized the utility of moisture-conserving technologies in the face of erratic rainfall (Zerssa et al., 2021).

Fig. 3. Proportion of gender in field day participation across different stakeholders

The results further showed a clear preference for mulching over bare plots, with most farmers expressing a strong willingness to continue using the technology. These findings align with those of Salama and Geyer (2023), who noted that plastic mulch is widely appreciated for its ability to improve crop yields by conserving soil moisture, suppressing weeds, and regulating soil temperature—factors that are especially critical in pineapple cultivation.

However, despite these advantages, the use of plastic mulch presents several challenges. Concerns were raised regarding cost and local availability, which mirror adoption barriers identified in Northern Ethiopia, where high input costs often deter resource-poor farmers from transitioning to modern horticultural practices (Tadesse et al., 2020). Furthermore, participants noted potential environmental impacts, such as the disruption of soil microflora and the risk of plastic residues entering the food chain. These environmental concerns are a subject of growing debate in Ethiopian agricultural research, as the long-term impact of non-biodegradable plastics on soil biodiversity remains under-studied compared to organic mulching alternatives (Neim et al., 2021).

Table 1. Participant farmers’ response (%) to assessment indicators under mulched (above) and non-mulched (below) conditions

Evaluation Indicator	Mulched				
	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)
Soil retained moisture	54.5	9.09	27.3	9.09	0.0
Productivity increased	45.5	45.5	0.0	9.09	0.0
Number of suckers increased	1.8	63.6	9.09	0.0	25.51
reduced weed pressure	67.5	30.4	2.1	0.0	0.0
Fruit marketability was good	54.5	27.2	0.0	9.09	9.091
Mulch management was easy	27.2	54.5	9.09	9.09	0.0
Want to continue using it	54.5	9.09	18.1	9.09	0.0

Evaluation Indicator	Non mulched				
	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)
Soil retained moisture	1.8	9.09	18.2	7.3	63.6
Productivity increased	27.2	9.09	0.0	63.6	0.0
Number of suckers increased	0.0	1.8	36.4	7.3	54.5
reduced weed pressure	1.3	2.2	2.8	28.7	64.8
Fruit marketability was good	27.2	1.8	9.09	60.1	1.8
Practice management was easy	9.09	0.0	1.8	7.3	81.8
Want to continue using it	9.09	1.8	9.09	24.6	55.5

3.4 Fruit Yield Performance

Pineapple yields under mulching conditions ranged from 86.3 t/ha in Tesso Kebele to 91.79 t/ha in Gambela Kebele (Table 2). The highest average fruit weights were recorded in Gambela (1.85 kg) and Tesso (1.69 kg). In contrast, yields from non-mulched plots were considerably lower, ranging from 51.0 t/ha in Tesso to 54.79 t/ha in Gambela, with average fruit weights of 1.35 kg and 1.29 kg, respectively. These results demonstrate a significant yield advantage of mulching over traditional practices. The yields achieved under mulching in this study are remarkably higher than those reported in Southwest Ethiopia, where typical yields in the Gojeb area range between 21 and 45 t/ha depending on planting time and management (Tewodros et al., 2022).

Furthermore, yield performance was generally higher in Gambela than in Tesso under both mulched and non-mulched conditions. This suggests inherent differences in environmental suitability or soil fertility between the two kebeles, a localized variation also observed in Jimma, where specific soil nutrient levels significantly influenced the success of pineapple intensification (Jimma Research Center, 2021). These findings are consistent with those of Alwis and Herath (2012), who reported that black polyethylene mulch significantly increases economic yield in pineapple production. In addition to yield gains, mulching was found to improve soil moisture retention at a depth of 30 cm during the first fruit harvest. This localized moisture conservation is particularly critical in the Sidama region, where erratic rainfall can otherwise lead to moisture stress, a factor identified as a primary constraint in other fruit-growing zones of Ethiopia (Amsalu & Tadesse, 2015; Zerssa et al., 2021).

Table 2. Pineapple fruit yield (tons ha⁻¹) under mulched and non-mulched conditions in Gambela and Tesso kebeles

Condition	Gambela (ton ha ⁻¹)			Tesso (ton ha ⁻¹)			Over all mean (ton ha ⁻¹)
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	
Mulching	72.6	121.5	91.79	67.4	115.3	86.3	89.05
Without Much	36.1	61	54.79	32.05	53.7	51	52.89
Mean			73.29			68.65	70.97

4. Conclusion and Recommendation

In conclusion, the application of black polyethylene mulch proved to be a highly effective intervention for pineapple production in the Aletachuko district. So the results revealed majority of them reported positive perceptions, highlighting improved soil moisture retention, reduced weed pressure, and improved productivity, marketable while also doubling yields compared to traditional practices. Although the technology was promising, adoption may be constrained by the cost and availability of polythene sheets in the area. Moreover, concern about the potential environmental impacts of plastic sheet on soil biodiversity and micro-flora need further research.

Based on these results, the following recommendations are made:

- **Technical Scale-up:** The use of black plastic mulch is technically recommended for pineapple growers in the Sidama region to bridge the current yield gap.
- **Market Integration:** Efforts should be made to improve the availability and affordability of polyethylene sheets in local markets, potentially through subsidies or collective purchasing by cooperatives.

- **Sustainable Innovation:** Further research is required to evaluate the long-term environmental impacts of plastic mulch on soil biodiversity and microflora. Future studies should also prioritize the development of sustainable plastic management strategies or the exploration of biodegradable alternatives to minimize the risk of soil contamination.

Disclaimer (Artificial Intelligence)

Author(s) hereby declare that NO generative AI technologies such as Large Language Models (ChatGPT, COPILOT, etc.) and text-to-image generators have been used during writing or editing of this manuscript.

Competing Interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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